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The Waste to Wealth Concept: Waste Market Operation in Delta State, Nigeria.

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The concept of waste to wealth which is the transformation of waste from an exhausted utility to a valuable commodity as a mechanism for effective solid waste management is yet to be properly utilized in Delta State. This study examined the waste market operation; identified the challenges facing its operation; proffered possible solutions necessary for the growth of the waste market, and also the need to harness the inherent economic and environmental benefits.

Keywords: Waste, Waste market operation, Waste to wealth, Environment, Delta State

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management has emerged as one of the greatest challenges facing state and local government environmental protection agencies in Nigeria. The volume of solid waste being generated continues to increase at a faster rate than the ability of the agencies to improve on the financial and technical resources needed to parallel this growth. Solid waste management in Nigeria is characterized by inefficient collection methods, insufficient coverage of the collection system and improper disposal of solid waste. The quantity of solid waste generated in urban areas in industrialized countries is higher than in developing countries; still municipal solid waste management remains inadequate in the latter. Solid waste in developing countries differs from developed countries. Most developing countries, including Nigeria have solid waste management problems different from those found in industrialized countries in areas of composition, density, political, and economic framework, waste amount, access to waste for collection, awareness and attitude. The wastes are heavier, wetter and more corrosive in developing cities than developed cities (Ogwueleka, 2009).

The concept of Waste-to-Wealth literally means moving waste from a platform of exhausted utility to valuable and desirable level. Its transformation: in engineering, requires some form of energy, and in economics requires factor of production. The latent issue here is that "waste" in itself can never be wealth otherwise generator will never discard it. Likewise, wealth is created and process of creating wealth has some cost implications that the market forces construe as the price. . This means that not all wastes are potentially of secondary benefit. In all, the slogan "waste-to-wealth connotes that waste management operations must transcend delivery of service to provision of goods or value like energy. The aim of this work is to examine the operation of waste markets in the State, identify the challenges facing its operation, and create awareness on the need to explore opportunities inherent in waste market for environmental and economic benefits.

Study Area

Delta State is located in the Niger-Delta region of Nigeria. It is located between longitude 5°.00C and 6°.45C East and latitude 5°.00 and 6°.00 North, with a total land area of 18,050 sq. km. It comprises twelve (12) major urban centres with Asaba as the capital city and Warri as her largest commercial city and the most populated in the state (Egun, 2009). The state has a population of 4,098,291 people made up of 2,674,306 males and 2,024,085 females; the major occupations are farming, fishing, hunting, oil exploration and the State Civil Service (Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, 2007). It has a tropical climate marked by two distinct seasons, namely, the

dry and rainy Seasons. The average annual rainfall in the coastal area is about 266.5cm and 190.5cm in the Northern fringes of the State. The temperature is high, ranging between 28°C and 34°C with an average temperature of 30°C (81°F) and vegetation varying from the mangrove swamps along the coast to evergreen forests and savannah in the north. Urbanization is driven mainly in the state by the rapid growth of formal education and the rural – urban wage differentials.

Waste Generated in the State

Income and economic growth have impact on the composition of wastes. Rotich et al. (2006) established a positive relationship between income levels and waste generation at the household level as High-income earners consume more packaged products, which result in a higher percentage of inorganic materials – metals, plastics, glass, and textile. Waste characteristics vary according to season, income level, population, social behaviour, climate, and industrial production, the size of markets for waste materials and the extent of urbanization, effectiveness of recycling, and work reduction (Hoorweg *et al.*, 1999).

Municipal solid waste composition in Delta State varies from one settlement to another and is dependent on the level of human and industrial activities taking place in these settlements, i.e. there are variations between urban/suburban and rural residential wastes. A closer observation shows that there exists a relative homogeneity of residential/ household waste generated across the state, with higher volumes in urban/ suburban areas which can be attributed to population. A new dimension to municipal solid waste which is a general feature of developing/ underdeveloped economies is the electronic waste (e-waste) ranging from bad/ faulty television display screen (tube), faulty/ damaged computer and electronic hard wares such as refrigerators and air conditioners.

In all of these, a common/ general component of solid waste generated in Delta State is plastics/ polythene products. This can be attributed to their diversity in usage ranging from household to industrial and the absence of a recovery system for them when compared to metal scraps and bottles. The high level of reuse of recyclable waste reflects the extent of poverty in the developing countries. In developing countries, waste stream is over 50% organic material (Hoorweg *et al.*, 1999).

Table 1: Percentage Composition/ Kg of Municipal Solid Waste in Delta State.

S/N	Composition	Dump Site 1	Dump Site 2	Dump Site 3	Average	%/ Kg
1	Plastics/ Polythene Products	0.23	0.19	0.22	0.21	21
2	Paper Products	0.17	0.18	0.19	0.18	18
3	Metal/ Aluminum Products	0.10	0.11	0.09	0.10	10
4	Vegetative materials/ Organic Compost	0.37	0.38	0.36	0.37	37
5	Ceramics	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.06	6
6	Textile Materials	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.05	5
7	Others e.g. Batteries, foams etc.	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	3

Note: That ash gotten from the incineration of waste such as papers and wood materials at dump sites which was part of the sample size collected was regarded as organic compost.

Wood and wood products: Waste generated from wood products which range from wood shavings in the sawmill, wood used at building/ construction sites to condemned finished wood products such as household/ office furniture, have little or no economic cash return value as they are mainly used as firewood for cooking, especially among the low income earners as it is presently the cheapest source of cooking energy in the country. The increase in poultry farming at subsistence level and as a Small/ Medium Scale Enterprise (SME) in the State concurrently lead to the increase and popularization of the litter system of poultry farming, where wood shavings from sawmills have found application as floor overlay for the collection of bird droppings and easy sanitation, thereby creating a waste market for it.

Organic and Vegetative Waste Materials: Waste in this category includes all waste generated from plants and animal materials either in their processed form such as food wastes from households and restaurants, or unprocessed form such as those generated from poor handling of food materials from the farm to the market. These wastes are sold to interested persons who use them as adjuncts for animal feed in farms. It is estimated that nearly a quarter of all household waste is organic and can be composted. Vegetative waste generated at household level constitute a very large percentage of organic waste found at dumpsites as they arrive the dumpsites already decomposing and mixed with other forms of waste, thereby making their recovery unsuccessful. In Nigeria, composting is undertaken in the open and the end product is used in farms as compost manure.

Metal Waste: this kind of waste popularly referred to as metal scraps are gotten from condemned gadgets, equipment and properties with metal components. Presently, this is the most lucrative waste material in the State as they are collected as scraps and sold back to the steel industries as adjunct raw materials for new product formulation.

Glass Materials: Waste from glass materials are of two types. Those generated from electrical appliances (e-waste) such as electric bulbs and computer display screens have no economic value presently in the State; thereby ending up in the various dumpsite. While those generated from packaging such as wine bottles, drugs and drinks have economic return value as they are collected and sold back to their producers who reuse them for the same purpose or sold in the retail market to small scale enterprises who use them for packaging their produce such as cowpea nuts.

Plastics/ Polythene Materials: Waste from this material is presently a challenge to effective solid waste management in the State as the rate of their reuse when compared to the rate of generation is very poor. At present there is no economic value attached to plastic waste in the State; this could be attributed to the challenge of sorting and grading of polythene products leading to their voluminous presence at dumpsites.

Waste Market Operation in the State

A waste picker is a person who salvages reusable or recyclable materials thrown away by others to sell or for personal consumption (Srinivas, 2011). Many terms are used to refer to people who salvage recyclables from the waste stream for sale or personal consumption. These terms include reclaimer, informal resource recoverer, recycler, salvager, scavenger, and waste picker. In 2008, participants of the First World Conference of Waste Pickers chose to use the term "waste picker" for English usage to facilitate global communication. Although the term "scavenger" is also commonly used, but many waste pickers find it demeaning due to the implied comparison with animals (Samson, 2008). "Waste picking" is an activity motivated purely by economic need. Forms of waste picking have been practiced since antiquity, but modern traditions of waste picking started during industrialization in the nineteenth century and over the past half century have expanded vastly in the developing world due to urbanization (Wilson, et al., 2005; Martin, 2007). This has led to millions of waste pickers worldwide, predominantly in developing countries, but increasingly in post-industrial countries as well (Gowan, 1997).

Waste pickers are key actors in the informal economy, as they make vital social, ecological, and economic contributions to their cities and help mitigate global warming. In many cities, they provide the only solid waste collection service. Yet they face many hardships, including stigma, exploitation by middlemen, and hazardous working and living conditions (Scheinberg and Anschütz, 2007). In Nigeria, recycling activities are not popular. However, the recovery of materials from wastes (scavenging) is practiced on a large scale. This type of recovery takes place at both legal and illegal dump sites where scavengers search continually for valuable metals, plastics, and bottles to be reused or for sale to buyers of different type of scraps.

Waste market in Delta State is presently an informal private sector market with unregulated activities, which is operated mainly by small enterprises and waste pickers who are driven by poverty and desire to earn a living. The practice of scavenging is a widespread occurrence at existing waste dump sites in Delta State as opposed in most developed countries, and is to be expected at new disposal sites unless policies and/or programs are implemented to prevent the practice.

The waste pickers operate by scavenging waste directly from the various dumpsites, the streets of neighbourhood in search of abandoned metal scraps and other useful recoverable waste. In the course of their activities, they are open to negotiations for the purchase of valuable waste from households and establishments. These collected wastes are then taken to the scrap market locations which are owned and operated by individuals who play the role of middlemen in the waste market business, especially for glass and metal waste. At the scrap shops the waste are further sorted, weighed and bought from the waste pickers. These middle men known as "Waste Traders" then take upon themselves the responsibility of transporting and supplying these wastes to the various industries which utilize them as raw materials.

The financial gain made by the waste picker is dependent on the purchasing price of the waste trader and also on the bargaining power with waste generators in situations when the waste has to be purchased. The increase in financial gain for the waste when the waste is gotten for free has resulted to their conspicuous presence at dumpsites, and some of them exhibiting criminal behaviours of stealing valuable materials from private and public premises in the State. In some cities, waste pickers have been known to steal, meltdown, and resell public property such as telephone electrical copper wires, steel fence, or manhole coverings (Martin, 2007).

METHODOLOGY

Data were collected through the use of a questionnaire in which questions pertaining to age, sex, level of education, occupation and issues affecting waste market operations were asked. Stratified random sampling was also used to provide appropriate representation of the societal classes in the population. A total of 200 people were interviewed, with the number of respondents evenly distributed on gender basis within the age group of 18 - 70 years.

Table 2: Demography Profile of Respondents

<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Sex</i>	
Male	50
Female	50
<i>Age</i>	
30 and below	20
31 – 50	40
51 – 60	35
Above 60	15
<i>Educational Level</i>	
No Education	3
Primary Education	30
Secondary Education	44
Tertiary and Above	23
<i>Main Occupation</i>	
Farming	08
Trading	38
Salary worker	20
Food Vendor	10
Skilled Workers (tailors, bricklayers etc.)	44

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 3, majority of the respondents (94 %) are concerned about the volume of waste presently generated in the State; an indication of an increase in environmental awareness among the citizenry but lack environmental consciousness as reflected in their attitude to waste generation and disposal (Egun, 2010). Pertaining to the purchase of and use of recycled waste, majority of the respondents (78%) responded positively as they were supportive of waste recycled products especially for plastic/ polythene products which is a major concern in the State; 11% of the respondents gave a negative response as they were of the notion that recycled products will not be durable and efficient as their un-recycled counterparts; and 11% of responses were uncertain, which could be attributed to their lack of knowledge about the concept of recycling. The use of compost fertilizer had 85% positive response and uncertain response of 15%. The high positive response is attributed to their background knowledge of cultural agricultural practices.

Awareness on the concept of waste separation before disposal showed a poor positive response (17%) and a high negative response (83%), an indication of lack of sensitization and enlightenment on the need for proper waste segregation before disposal, as present enlightenment done on waste management has been centred on proper disposal of waste using waste bins/ tanks with the aim of preventing water erosion and flooding as a result of waste blockage of water drainages; and having a cleaner environment. Those who responded positively to waste separation/ sorting before disposal were mostly those who have had the opportunity of living in the Western/ developed countries where it is been practiced; and are not presently doing so because of the absence of adequate facilities.

Also, on the issue of participation in the waste market operation; 87% of the respondents gave a positive response, 5% responded negatively and 13% of the respondents were uncertain. Those who responded negatively saw the job as demeaning, which can be attributed to the present perception of the job. Those who responded positively have been involved in the waste market operation indirectly as they have on several occasions sold household recoverable waste such as bottles, metal scraps, newspapers and abandoned electronics to waste pickers/ scavengers for a token amount of money or in exchange for other useful household items; and would be encouraged to participate more if Government provide certain incentives necessary to make the market lucrative.

Table 3: Respondents replies to issues affecting waste market operation

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>1. Concern about the volume of waste generated.</i>	
Yes	94
No	6
<i>2. Purchase of products made from recycled waste</i>	
Yes	78
No	11
Uncertain	11
<i>3. Use of Compost Fertilizer</i>	
Yes	85
No	-
Uncertain	15
<i>4. Participation in Waste Market Operation</i>	
Yes	87
No	5
Uncertain	13
<i>5. Awareness on the concept of waste separation before disposal</i>	
Yes	17
No	83

RECOMMENDATION

Delta State has serious challenges with its waste management from generation through storage, treatment, to disposal; non availability of enough storage facilities, treatment technologies, and good methods of disposal for its waste. The problem of solid wastes in the State that has become an intractable nuisance is the indiscriminate dumping of refuse, as citizens continue to exhibit apathetic and lackadaisical attitudes towards matters relating to personal hygiene and environmental cleanliness, of which waste management in general is its focus, and should not be over looked.

Adewole (2009) in a study on Lagos State Nigeria observed that the individual attitude to waste disposal leaves more to be desired. The absence of the culture/ etiquette of waste separation before disposal is a major challenge facing the waste recovery market as goods when immediately discarded as waste having economic value loose it as they get mixed up with other waste. Notable examples of such are paper based products such as cartoons and polythene products used for packaging goods, which are presently not properly handled for disposal leading to their ending up in waste dump sites where their fate is left to nature. There is need for the proper definition of the concept of wet, dry and recyclable waste so that the citizens will be able to separate their garbage before it is picked up by the waste management operators. The State Government should initiate a program of waste handling and collection that includes waste separation at source. The program should include provision of waste bins in the entire local government areas. The bins should be with wheels and should be 3 in every location for bio-degradable, recyclables and hazardous. Modern deep collection containers are recommended for cities and towns in the State.

According to Zurbrugg (1999), waste generation is conditioned to an important degree by people's attitudes towards waste especially their patterns of material use and waste handling, their interest in waste reduction and minimization, the degree to which they separate wastes and the extent to which they refrain from indiscriminate dumping and littering. Addressing the problem of lack of environmental consciousness among people living in Delta State requires a holistic and integrated system approach involving the State's Ministries of Education – especially in the formal education system, Information and Public Orientation – formal and informal education systems, Environment and Sanitation; Youth and Development adopting the grass-root mobilization concepts for the environment starting from the individual, then the household and on to the entire society at large. This will promote responsible environmental behaviour amongst the citizenry and sustainable development in the State (Egun, 2010). Programmes to disseminate knowledge and to improve behaviour patterns and attitudes regarding waste management are therefore critical. For such programmes to succeed, it must be based on sound understanding of the social and cultural characteristics of the communities. These inputs do not necessarily have to be financial. For example, waste recycling can be promoted through consumer campaigns encouraging citizens to co-operate in waste separation and promoting to them the purchase of recycled products (Joon and Kumar, 2009; Nabegu, 2010). Though attitudes towards solid waste may be positively influenced by public information and educational measures, improved waste handling patterns can hardly be maintained in the absence of practical waste disposal options. Awareness-building measures should therefore be coordinated with improvements in waste collection services, whether public or community managed.

Legislation: Although the Federal government has taken adequate legislative steps to tackle environmental problems, including solid-waste management such as the setting up of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) (FEPA, 1990). Establishment of State Environmental Protection Commission (EPC) to complement the efforts of FEPA in each State. However, much success is yet to be achieved, largely because of the weakness of the enabling legislation and the inability of the relevant agencies to enforce some of the laws, leaving much to be desired.

One of the unique features of the waste market is that its major driving force is hinged on the policy developed by the Government. The importance of the Government providing fiscal and regulatory consistency and transparency to underpin investment in the move from landfill to waste recovery infrastructure development cannot be undermined, as policies/ laws which aim at dissuading the disposal of waste at landfill sites and making waste recovery and utilization cheaper, impacts positively on the market. Some potential Government policy options are:

- a. Provide greater certainty around long- term direction of fiscal and regulatory frame work as it pertains to waste disposal as this will motivate investment in the market/ sector. According to the Chartered Institute of Waste Management, "The worst thing is when Government prevaricates or even changes its mind. It is very frustrating when you make an investment because the rules are about to change and then the Government changes its mind and your investment has gone to waste. We need good notice so we can plan and we need consistency and clear direction" (Chartered Institute of Waste Management).
- b. Redefine municipal waste to include more trade waste; promote innovations in collection mechanisms.
- c. Increasing landfill tax as a way of ensuring that market incentives created reflect wider costs of disposal.
- d. Take steps to increase availability of finance generally to companies involved in the waste market for investment in waste recovery technologies (Defra, 2010). Such laws when enacted and implemented will create multiple impacts in the waste market operation positively, such as the survival and sustenance of recycling companies and the economic viability of waste.

Acknowledging the huge disparity in the socioeconomic conditions of developed nations and developing nations like Nigeria, there is need for a different approach in achieving sustainable and effective solid waste management in Nigeria that will take into cognisance the political, institutional, social, financial, economic and technical aspects of solid waste management. Developed countries enjoy a relative abundance of capital and have high labour cost while developing countries like Nigeria have a relative scarcity of capital and an abundance of unskilled and inexpensive labour. So any waste management systems with intensive in capital that save in labour cost does not make sense to us. Nigeria needs low capital cost and labour intensive solutions that reduce poverty.

Waste picking provides a cushion for many who lose their jobs during times of war, crisis, and economic downturn in countries that do not have welfare systems. It is also one of the few work opportunities available to people who lack formal education or job experience (Martin, 2007). The role of scavengers is very important in the planning, implementation, and operation of land disposal sites as the occurrence of scavenging between the point of waste generation and the disposal location influences the quantities of waste that will be disposed, therefore this aspect of scavenging must be taken into account during the process of estimating waste quantities and characteristics in the State.

There is need for the Government and Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC) to intervene in the welfare of waste pickers/ scavengers in the State and Country at large by organizing them into a structured union as obtainable in other countries such as the Waste Collector's Association of Bogotá (ARB) in Columbia; Latin American Waste Picker Network (LAWPN)—an organization that now represents waste pickers movements from 16 countries; The South African Waste Picker organization in South Africa; Indian waste pickers union known as KKKPKP and The Alliance of Indian Waste Pickers (AIW), one of Asia's largest waste pickers associations with a national network of 35 organizations in 22 cities (Samson, 2008). This will contribute immensely in giving their activity a legal backing, help in checking and regulating their activities and give them a social status as waste pickers' perceived poverty and lack of sanitation makes some people uncomfortable or fearful and view them as a nuisance or source of shame for their communities (Gowan, 2010). Also their effective organization will empower them with political influence as they will be able to demand recognition and compensation from the State for their environmental and economic contributions; cooperatively be able to secure uniforms, safety equipment, and work permits leading to increase workplace dignity and safety; workplace; and increase their selling power/ earnings by forming partnerships with business and Government.

Government should come in to harness the abundant manpower of scavengers/ waste pickers by providing safety complaint wears and working instruments to make the working environment safer and encouraging for the participation of youths thereby creating employment. Their role in the reduction of waste in dump sites should and must be captured in the planning of effective solid waste management and waste marked operations as they can be incorporated in the proposed waste separation - collection system which is the primary backbone and the initial driving force/ commitment needed to be made by the government to make available various waste materials as precursor and additive raw materials for industries.

CONCLUSION

Waste creation is part of human endeavour but the disposal will be neglected until Government creates incentives, preferably market – based incentives that will encourage both people and enterprises to dispose their waste in an appropriate way. This is paramount because the implication of proper waste disposal has led to a huge expenditure on public health, reduction in productivity of the populace and reduction of life expectancy (Thisday, 2010). Today, when waste management service is delivered and cost paid for by the generator (providing employment), it means waste has provided wealth too and can be construed as waste-to-wealth. With this extension, effective waste management has become not only service but an instrument for fighting poverty. Government should not only conceive waste management as service but a war against poverty and poor living environment for actualization of oneself.

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